

Organizational culture as a facilitator of diversity and inclusion in the organization

A cultura organizacional como facilitadora da inclusão e diversidade na organização

La cultura organizativa como facilitadora de la inclusión y diversidad en la organización

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Abstract:

The objective of this article is to investigate how organizational culture impacts inclusion and diversity practices within the organization, while also examining the policies adopted by companies to ensure that these practices are present and applied in ways that promote employee well-being, safety, and development. To understand how organizations operationalize inclusion and diversity in practice, a qualitative methodology was employed through semi-structured interviews conducted with individuals who are part of diverse groups. The results highlight the need for organizations to address these issues with seriousness and respect, ensuring that they are not merely marketing strategies but genuine commitments capable of fostering more inclusive and equitable work environments.

Keywords: *Organizational culture; Organization; Diversity; Inclusion.*

Resumo:

Este artigo tem como objetivo investigar de que maneira a cultura organizacional impacta as práticas de inclusão e diversidade dentro da organização e quais são as políticas adotadas pelas empresas para assegurar que tais práticas existam e sejam aplicadas de forma a garantir a qualidade de vida, segurança e desenvolvimento do colaborador. Com o intuito de identificar como as organizações operacionalizam a inclusão e a diversidade na prática, foi utilizada a metodologia qualitativa através de entrevistas semiestruturadas aplicadas com pessoas que fazem parte de grupos diversos. Os resultados evidenciam a necessidade de que as organizações abordem essas questões com seriedade e respeito para que não sejam tratadas apenas como estratégias de marketing, mas sim como compromissos genuínos com capacidade de promover ambientes de trabalho mais inclusivos e equitativos.

Palavras-chave: *Cultura organizacional; Organização; Diversidade.; Inclusão.*

Resumen:

El objetivo de este artículo es investigar de qué manera la cultura organizacional impacta las prácticas de inclusión y diversidad dentro de la organización, así como las políticas adoptadas por las empresas para asegurar que tales prácticas existan y se apliquen de forma que garanticen la calidad de vida, seguridad y desarrollo del

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colaborador. Con el fin de identificar cómo las organizaciones llevan a la práctica la inclusión y la diversidad, se utilizó una metodología cualitativa mediante entrevistas semiestructuradas realizadas a personas que forman parte de distintos grupos. Los resultados destacan la necesidad de que las organizaciones aborden estas cuestiones con seriedad y respeto, para que no sean tratadas únicamente como estrategias de marketing, sino como compromisos genuinos capaces de promover entornos de trabajo más inclusivos y equitativos.

Palabras clave: *Cultura organizacional; Organización; Diversidad; Inclusión.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, the topic of diversity and inclusion has been widely discussed, particularly in the context of organizational agendas. Demographic differences related to gender, race, physical ability, sexual orientation, age, ethnicity, and cultural background, among others, have an impact that is reflected in an organization's values, objectives, and ethical standards, shaping its organizational culture. Inclusion becomes an important component for respectfully embracing all these differences.

Inclusion refers to the fair treatment of all groups, where everyone feels welcomed, has equal opportunities, and is represented in different roles and levels within the organization. Inclusion is combined with the perception of acceptance, promoting the feeling of being valued and welcomed as part of the team at all levels. Therefore, inclusion transcends diversity, and its effectiveness depends on proper diversity management, creating an environment that lets the full development of employees' potential in achieving the organization's objectives (BASTOS; BORGES-ANDRADE; ZANELLI, 2004).

Taking these aspects into consideration, the relevance of evaluating the topic is clear, given that it permeates society and is reflected in the market. Therefore, this article aims to identify the characteristics of an organizational culture that practices inclusion and diversity. From a specific perspective, we analyze reports to explore the potential benefits of aligning organizational culture and inclusion in the development of both the organization and its employees.

Therefore, the research question that guides this article is: "How does organizational culture influence inclusion and diversity?" It aims to identify which inclusion and diversity policies companies incorporate into their organizational culture and which can generate development opportunities for their employees and their brand. Along the same lines, it hopes to establish a likeness between the potential of a diverse environment and how valuing differences and uniqueness can promote the effective alignment of strategies and objectives, as well as a competitive advantage in the job market.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Organizational Culture

The word "culture" originates from social anthropology and, in a general approach, broadly translates the experiences, practices, and behaviors of any human group. In other words, it is the set of knowledge, traditions, values, beliefs, and practices that are transmitted from one generation to the next, shaping the way individuals experience and interpret the world around them. Thus, it is possible to say that culture represents the collective heritage and continuous evolution of life forms and human expressions that characterize a given social group (TATAGIBA, 2022, p. 3). In Delvas' (2017, p. 6) conception, organizations are characterized as a group of people and, therefore, also present their own culture.

An organization is a group of people who work together in a division of labor to achieve a common purpose. It is a social instrument through which people

combine their efforts and work together to achieve a common goal. Therefore, it is possible to perceive the great importance of the role of individuals, groups, and teams in the behavior of organizations (CHIAVENATO, 2021, p. 28).

Dias (2012, p. 212) says that organizational culture can be interpreted as a subculture of the more general culture and that, then, it can be defined as a system of shared values and beliefs that interacts with people, the organization's structures, decision-making processes and composition control systems to produce norms of behavior.

According to Tatagiba (2022, p. 4), culture is the most important part of a corporation because it is responsible for all other elements that formulate the organization. An institution's organizational culture determines its strategies, hiring practices, the type of people it attracts, and how teams are organized.

In addition to the bonds and connections established through organizational culture, norms and regulations are also developed to guide and direct employee behavior. Based on this behavior, organizational members will adapt to its essence, adjusting their actions according to the organization's characteristic routines, strategies, and work practices (ARAÚJO; COSTA; FERREIRA, 2021, p. 4).

In organizations, the human resources department plays a prominent role in disseminating the institution's organizational culture through the development of integration, training and development programs, rewards, through the creation of profiles compatible with the positions offered, benefits packages, among other actions equally directed to the group's survival interests (FONSECA, 2021, p. 93).

Hence, Dias (2011, p. 17) understands that whenever we discuss culture, we must keep in mind humanity in all its richness and plurality of forms of existence, and adds that when we talk about culture, or cultures, it is possible to contemplate diversity.

2.2 Diversity

Diversity has become a relevant point and a recurring topic of debate today. However, this issue has always existed thanks to the colonization process that fostered the formation of a culturally diverse and pluralistic global population. The term is marked by its broad scope, as it is understood to encompass individual differences between each person. It can refer to factors such as gender, age, race, sexual orientation, or religion.

Nkomo and Cox Jr. (1998) acknowledge that to achieve clarity in the language and meaning of diversity, there is a need to structure the concept better, as the term is incomplete: diversity in what?

Among dozens of definitions of the topic, Fleury (2000, p. 20) highlights:

Diversity is defined as a mix of people with different identities interacting within the same social system. In these systems, the majority and minority groups coexist. Majority groups are those whose members have historically enjoyed advantages in terms of economic resources and power over others.

By correlating the author's definition with the current Brazilian scenario, we confirm the timelessness of her words, as throughout history, well-known groups

that have been marginalized and excluded from exercising their citizenship have been defined by who they are.

2.3 Inclusion and Diversity Management in Organizations

According to Fleury (2000), organizational diversity programs began to emerge in history around the 1960s in the USA with the launch of Affirmative Action. Action, which refers to targeted policies that allocate resources to benefit people belonging to discriminated groups and victims of their social exclusion in society. In Brazil, the topic is relatively new, emerging around the 1990s, thanks to the presence of subsidiaries of American multinationals. Nevertheless, it is not legally mandated, unlike in the North American context.

According to Gomes and Renner (2020, p. 33), diversity is a significant factor in the business model of many organizations. Coexisting with differences, whether in terms of gender, race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, or other factors, has a significant impact on corporate results and fosters a responsible and sustainable business. Following this line of thought, the authors continue to argue that organizations have a fundamental role in promoting relevant transformations that contribute to changing reality, whether through actions focused on their internal stakeholders or through positive actions in their relationships with the value chain, through their presence in the communities where they operate, or by exerting positive influence on other stakeholders.

Managers from different areas understand that the more heterogeneous the composition of a team, in terms of race, gender, ethnicity, sexual orientation, religion, among others, the more different experiences will compose it, bringing varied concepts, ideas, world views and contributing to the creativity and innovation so necessary in the corporate scenario (ANTUNES; TOLDO, 2014, p. 2).

Gomes and Renner (2020, p. 28) understand that the inclusion of diverse groups within companies aims to implement practices that generate value for the business, promoting a broader and more assertive vision, and addressing issues of social responsibility.

When examining diversity management in organizations, we can affirm that, when implemented effectively, it has the capacity to expand the institution's access to a diverse set of skills, competencies, and ideas. This more strategic approach not only enriches the organizational environment but also enhances the corporation's innovation and adaptability (JUDGE; ROBBINS, 2014, p. 22).

3. METHOD

This article aims to analyze the presence of diversity within organizations and how an organizational culture that truly practices inclusion can strategically employ these practices to supply healthier and more attractive environments. Therefore, to achieve this specific objective, we employed exploratory-descriptive research, which, according to Caleffe and Moreira (2006), refines ideas or uncover intuitions, with the primary objective of describing the characteristics of a given population or phenomenon. Regarding the approach, we used a qualitative approach, which, according to Caleffe and Moreira (2006), explores the characteristics of individuals and scenarios that cannot be easily

described numerically. The data are verbal and collected through observation, description, and recording.

3.1 Bibliographic Analysis

At this stage, scientific research was analyzed around the theme of organizational culture, diversity, and inclusion in organizations, through academic materials such as books, scientific articles, monographs, and related research.

3.2 Semi-structured Interviews

To ensure the application of a target audience-centered approach, qualitative analysis was employed through semi-structured interviews and Bardin's (2011) data analysis technique, which is divided into preliminary analysis, material exploration, and result processing. These stages facilitate the understanding, use, and application of a given piece of content. Additionally, Fraser and Gondim (2004) emphasize that individual interviews may be indicated when the aim is to gain a deeper understanding of the meanings and, hence, the individual's perspective on a phenomenon.

The interview guide questions were designed to allow interviewees to discuss their experiences and perceptions based on their experiences within the organization they work for or in organizations they have worked for. A total of 14 individuals participated in the interviews, representing diverse backgrounds in gender, race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, and disability.

The method chosen for the interviews was the snowball method, which is based on the authors' contact network and the relationship network of these contacts. According to Vinuto (2014, p.3), this is a non-probabilistic sampling method where key people are identified to respond and indicate other people who can help by responding to the survey, consequently increasing the amount of information until theoretical saturation is reached (GLASER; STRAUSS, 1967).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 1 presents details of each person who took part in the data collection process, detailing their age and how the person identifies with the topic:

Table 1 – Characteristics of the people interviewed

Interviewees	Age	With relation to diversity
Interviewee S	26 years old	Black and bisexual.
Interviewee ES	28 years old	Woman, black and pansexual.
Interviewee GS	27 years old	Black and <i>gay</i> .
Interviewee V	25 years old	<i>Gay</i> .
Interviewee T	30 years old	Woman, black and bisexual.
Interviewee GL	26 years old	<i>Gay</i> .
Interviewee D	30 years old	Woman, black and lesbian.
Interviewee R	25 years old	A woman and bisexual.
FM Interviewee	30 years old	A woman and bisexual.
Interviewee ME	20 years old	Woman, bisexual and aromantic.
Interviewee C	29 years old	Black and <i>gay</i> .
Person interviewed FC	29 years old	Brown, non-binary and bisexual.
Interviewee P	19 years old	Woman, bisexual and person with disabilities.
Interviewee RB	43 years old	A woman, black and a person with disabilities.

Source: Authors (2024)

At the end of the interviews, a literal transcription of all responses was conducted. Then, using the Flores method (1994), an analysis was performed that consisted of segmenting, coding, and categorizing the excerpts obtained during the interviews. Segmentation, coding and categorization of interviews.

Table 2 – Meta category “Organizational culture aligned with inclusion and diversity” (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
PEPI	Includes perceptions that few companies actually [...]	R1 - Most companies do not are aligned and are also not prepared for this. You need people [...]
PEPI	[...] practice inclusion and diversity	<p>[...] more capable, more literate people who are truly allies of the cause, not for personal gain but rather out of affinity and out of respect.</p> <p>R2 - Most companies still use inclusion in the organization as a <i>marketing strategy</i> and not as a rooted culture, to value diversity, so I believe it is not yet fully aligned.</p> <p>R3 - ... is still entirely profit-driven. It is much easier to make money when you practice diversity, principally because, in addition to the differences you can leverage in each person, you end up gaining prominence in the market and in social issues.</p> <p>A4 - I do not think so. There is still no racial or gender equality. Straight, white men still hold the most prominent positions.</p> <p>R5 - Because it is a much-discussed topic, companies try to consider it more. At the same time, there are many gaps between planning a more diverse company and achieving inclusion and diversity in that environment. They care about inclusion, but often prioritize profit, which remarkably hinders the achievement of these goals.</p> <p>A6 - There is still a long way to go. This is because the job market, in many cases, adopts these guidelines to meet targets, without focusing on promoting significant changes in the workplace.</p> <p>R7 - No company can be 100% aligned in all aspects of diversity, accessibility, and gender equity; not everything will be met by most companies.</p> <p>R8 - I think it is very common to see companies, whether in meetings, interviews or integrations, among others... stating that they are inclusive and in favor of diversity, when this all goes beyond hiring (which, let us face it, is extremely low).</p> <p>A9 - I observe, unfortunately, that most organizations are concerned with meeting corporate quotas, and not in ensuring the diversity and inclusion of their employees as a social concern.</p> <p>R10 - ...not if you are a person with a disability.</p> <p>R11 - I do believe that this culture does exist, but due to a law that requires the inclusion of quotas in companies, so that they do not pay fines.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 3 – Meta category “Alignment of organizational culture with inclusion and diversity” (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
GEB	Includes perceptions of benefits generated by the practice	<p>R1 - People work better when they are happy— not just happy, but when they also feel their existence is respected. Aligning culture with diversity will automatically bring benefits to the company, as people will work more effectively and give their best for their own benefit and the company's.</p> <p>R2 - When people feel included and valued, they automatically have better performance and engagement results... When they feel heard, it generates more innovation and creativity through their ideas.</p> <p>R3 - Not only in relation to profit but also, to human capital. When a company values its diversity, it promotes people within that diversity. It shows that there are no differences, no barriers for people, that everyone can achieve something. Although some details are still missing, it still yields many benefits.</p> <p>R4 - It not only brings benefits to the company but also to society. It is a way to reduce prejudice, broaden our outlook, and expose a different perspective to the workplace.</p> <p>R5 - The more different people involved in different projects and with diverse experience involved in a project, the richer it will be and automatically these people will want to include more people there, all as willingly as possible, and this unimaginably changes the work environment.</p> <p>R6 - Promoting innovation through Different perspectives can result in creative solutions, improving the work environment and, consequently, increasing employee satisfaction and productivity. Furthermore, it makes the company more attractive to new talent in the job market.</p> <p>R7 - Having this inclusion, the person ends up feeling even a little better for being in that environment.</p> <p>R8 - When a company is committed to diversity and offers resources for this, it is a good attraction both from a professional perspective (where great talents compete to be part of the company) and from the public's perspective, giving positive visibility to the organization.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 3 – Meta category “Alignment of organizational culture with inclusion and diversity” (part 2)

Code	Category Definition	Units
GEB	Includes perceptions of benefits generated by the practice	<p>R9 - Each person brings with them their own load that may require different views and a more personal approach for each. Suppose a company, for example, has a standard of a single team per group/class. How can it improve its communication and service to understand better and serve all the remaining groups/classes?</p> <p>R10 - The plurality of employee experiences enriches the organizational culture, generating thrilling results.</p> <p>R11 - ...can generate significant benefits for companies. In addition to tax breaks, it improves the company's image and fosters innovation and creativity, thanks to each company's culture.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 4 – Meta category “Diversity among employees within the organization” (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
EDO	Includes perceptions about the presence of diversity in the organization where you work	<p>R1 - There is diversity of race, gender and sexual orientation.</p> <p>R2 - There is a lot of it, of all types. I can see sexual diversity, generational diversity... and racial diversity too.</p> <p>R3 - There is diversity among employees in terms of ethnicity, race, gender, sexual orientation and disability, and it is a safe and welcoming environment for everyone.</p> <p>R4 - Most are <i>gay men</i>, but there are two non-binary people... there are also a lot of bisexual people.</p> <p>R5 - Yes, there is much diversity in terms of race and sexuality. Nevertheless, at the same time, it is not a safe place to be fully yourself.</p> <p>R6 - Yes, there are, all types.</p>
ADD	Includes insights into the lack of diversity in the organization where you work	<p>R1 - I do not think so. It is, well, you can see it, but it is at lower levels than the company. So, if we look at senior leadership, the board of directors, which is the company's top brass, is extremely niche. The company even has a museum with photos of everyone on the board, and you seem to be seeing the same person: a white man with white hair and a suit.</p> <p>R2 - It exists, but it is not totally inclusive diversity, right? We see ethnic diversity, [...]</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 4 – Meta category “Diversity among employees within the organization” (part 2)

Code	Category Definition	Units
ADD	Includes insights into the lack of diversity in the organization where you work	<p>[..] though, we do not see much diversity in terms of gender, such as trans people, nor much diversity in terms of disabilities. R3 - I still see tiny inclusion within my company regarding disabilities. I think that is a problem.</p> <p>R4 - Not racial... I believe it reflects the society we live in. We still see that Black people are the most disadvantaged when it comes to holding positions, especially higher positions... Furthermore, obviously, we cannot forget trans people, who, I believe, regardless of gender, race, or sexual orientation, are also the most disadvantaged in society in general. They are truly the group of people with the fewest opportunities in the workplace.</p> <p>R5 - Regarding race, in the past, there were many people black, but nowadays I do not see many.</p> <p>R6 - We are not advanced when it comes to trans people. I also think there is room for improvement in terms of disability and racial representation. On my team, for example, there were no Black people.</p> <p>R6 - Not much...</p> <p>R7 - No. Because many companies are not prepared to deal with people with disabilities.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 5 – Meta category “Influence of leaders and managers on the culture for inclusion and diversity” (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
ILGE	Includes insights into the impact of leaders' and managers' behavior	<p>R1 - ... is who multiplies all the company information, so leadership is there to ensure that the top of the company can communicate with the middle, the sides, the bottom, with everything, they are the multipliers of all types of information, of culture, so, if leadership is not aligned, it is, automatically, their peers or even their subordinates cannot also align with the company's culture.</p> <p>R2 - They are vital, as they are Responsible for influencing, even modeling, and shaping how diversity is handled in that environment. Through leaders, it is possible to create a safer environment, implement concrete practices, and ensure that diversity is not just a word, but an action within the organization.</p> <p>R3 - I think a good manager can include diverse people on his team for great contributions, so [...]</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 5 – Meta category “Influence of leaders and managers on the culture for inclusion and diversity” (part 2)

Code	Category Definition	Units
ILGE	Includes insights into the impact of leaders' and managers' behavior	<p>[...] for the company and this contribution, I think it is largely up to the manager to take the lead in including this type of audience. R4 - This decision is not solely up to the leader; they directly influence it because they show that through diversity, the team can achieve the expected result and can take advantage of each other's knowledge to achieve a common result.</p> <p>R5 - So it is imperative that the manager really knows how to include these people without creating an environment in which these people feel used in favor of a market agenda and not in favor of the people.</p> <p>R6 - ...when they demonstrate their commitment to diversity and adopt inclusive practices, they create an environment where everyone feels respected and valued. This leadership makes all the difference and creates a more welcoming organizational culture.</p> <p>R7 - ...are the main disseminators of organizational culture. If they are open to discussing diversity and listening to employees, it is possible to convey to management the vision of the company's lower-level positions.</p> <p>R8 - I believe that leaders can have a portion of the voice needed to change this, yes, but I would say that it is not just them...</p> <p>R9 - ... many employees are inspired by the attitude and values of their managers.</p> <p>R10 - ...yes, because they need to set examples of respect, empathy, and valuing all forms of inclusion.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 6 – Meta category “Practices adopted by organizations to value diversity” (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
PDO	Practices carried out in the company where you work or worked	<p>R1 - I can only think of two things right now, one of them is... they make recurring posts in an <i>email newsletter</i>, they make some posts on social media like that, but for example, selection process, yeah, meetings, affinity groups, these are things that I do not see much.</p> <p>R2 - There is an inclusive recruitment policy, a diversity and inclusion committee, and a promotion of a safe environment with active listening.</p> <p>R3 - ..."diversifies AeC", I work for AeC, and this program brings highlights, highlighted scenarios for people who come from different cultures who already present different doctrines that demonstrate [...]</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 6 – Meta category “Practices adopted by organizations to value diversity” (part 2)

Code	Category Definition	Units
PDO	Practices carried out in the company where you work or worked	[...] and represents this diversity, we have a female mentoring program, it is something the company is committed to, we have referrals, we also have programs for the inclusion of people with disabilities... R4 - I have worked in companies that guaranteed the hiring of trans people for the trial period so that these women at least had the chance to try a formal profession. R5 - ... conducts training for programs focused on diversity and inclusion, addressing issues of communication, unconscious bias and empathy in the workplace. R6 - Inclusion committees such as the Diversity committee and the sexual orientation group. R7 - The company I work for offers courses for people with disabilities, and educational campaigns about sexuality, etc.
WITH	A few practices in the company where you work	R1 - There are a few in my company; on the other hand, we have the practice of having a more diverse selection process ... R2 - The only thing they do there is respect people's social name, which, for me, is the bare minimum... apart from that, I believe nothing else.
NPD	Lack of practices in the company where you work	R1 - I am not aware of the existence of these practices in my company. R2 - In the company where I work today, I do not really see a practice. R3 - None. They only hold events and exhibitions about diversity, and all these events are aimed at external audiences. They are rarely aimed at employees themselves. R4 - Honestly, I have never worked at one that adopted such practice. The most I have seen of this were companies that did not discriminate but also did not seek to encourage or raise awareness about being more respectful or improving the work environment. R5 - I am not aware of any general program for people of all types to democratically access/occupy internal spaces within the organization. R6 – There were no practices.

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 7 – Meta category “Discrimination and prejudice in the workplace” (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
PIO	Includes insights into how the company handles	R1 - They have a 0800 number, a hotline for reporting, that kind of thing in case there are, yes, issues that need to be worked on, but it is something very internal, you do not see [...]

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 7 – Meta category “Discrimination and prejudice in the workplace” (part 2)

Code	Category Definition	Units
PIO	Includes insights into how the company handles	<p>[...] the leader talking about it, most meetings are not about it, so it is something that happens a lot behind the scenes.</p> <p>R2 - ... It should be a well-used system, but it is flawed because situations of, I can say, prejudice, racism occur, but many managers do not know how to deal with the situation.</p> <p>R3 - ... in the companies I have worked for, no There were many ways to deal with prejudice. Often, the "jokes" came from managers and leaders themselves. This was all when prejudice was not blatant and used extremely pejorative adjectives. And companies always fail to offer any support regarding this, simply covering up any such behavior.</p> <p><i>Compliance</i> policy, to keep the company culture always aligned.</p>
INCO	Includes insights into the impact on organizational culture	<p>R1 - ... the way the company deals with these issues directly shows who it is, whether it truly values inclusion and respect or whether they are just words or <i>marketing ploys</i>.</p> <p>R2 - ... companies need to have a very effective way to combat intolerance and any type of prejudice. ... It is essential to maintain culture and diversity, and even more so, diversity and respect among employees.</p> <p>R3 – The way the company deals with such situations creates a more comfortable environment for minorities present in the company.</p> <p>R4 - If you always see negative things being fought, you condition your brain to also police itself for possible situations that need to be fought, and this, in the workplace, where we usually do not have much of a voice as the working class, let alone as part of our diversity, is extremely important!</p> <p>R5 - The way a company handles discrimination says a lot about its culture. Having clear and effective policies to address these issues shows that the company truly cares about inclusion and helps create a more positive environment for everyone.</p> <p>R6 - Often, when a company does not deal with discrimination issues or neglects to report them, this view ends up becoming a mark on the culture, and even if they try to recover later, [...]</p>
PIO	Includes insights into how the company handles	<p>[...] it is much more difficult to make old employees, customers and new audiences change their view of the company.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Table 8 – Meta category "Strongly established organizational culture with inclusion and diversity" (part 1)

Code	Category Definition	Units
REA	Includes insights into creating a safer and more attractive environment for people	<p>R1 - ... who is part of groups marginalized, whether in ethnicity, sexuality, gender, yes, they are already worried about being able to return home alive with society itself... Those who go to the company want to feel safe the way they feel at home, sometimes people are not even safe at home, so they are going to work precisely to escape this reality. ... if the company is well aligned, the culture is well worked on this aspect, people will feel better, they will feel safe to work, to give their best.</p> <p>R2 - Working in a company that has an established culture makes people feel like they belong there, makes people speak well of the company, and consequently makes it more attractive to other people.</p> <p>R3 - ... people have the issue of security in being able to be who they are, right, and there is the issue of security in being able to work more broadly without being judged.</p> <p>R4 - With diversity, people who have a core competence for that job, who were previously hidden away, afraid to apply for a position, can see the company's prominence in this diverse environment, which is a safe place to work. They will be interested, they will try, they will step outside of where they are.</p> <p>R6 - Once I do not feel like a pawn used only for profit, I develop the confidence I need to take more risks in my career without losing part of who I am!</p> <p>R7 - When diversity is valued in a company, employees feel more included, respected, recognized, and comfortable sharing their opinions and being themselves. This fosters a safer work environment that promotes a sense of belonging.</p> <p>R8 - An organizational culture that includes and respects diversity among people ends up attracting more people to that environment.</p>
REA	Includes insights into creating a safer and more attractive environment for people	<p>R9 - As an LGBT person, I would feel much safer in a company that I know believes in the importance of diversity and that strongly supports speaking out in the event of any prejudiced attitude from an employee.</p> <p>R10 - A strong culture alone is not enough. This must be communicated to all positions, ensuring that any behavior that is not tolerated is eliminated, regardless of the person's position.</p> <p>R11 - ...it made the environment better and lighter, it left me free to be who I was without fear of any judgment, and I dare say that it helped me to guarantee good results in the company, as it explored my creativity much better.</p> <p>R12 - ...the environment has abundant influence, and if you have a very clear and objective policy, respect and inclusion will attract more people.</p>

Source: Authors (2024)

Figure 1 – Relations between metalanguage and codes

Source: Authors (2024)

Based on the analysis of interviews conducted with individuals involved in the diversity field, it is manifest that inclusion and diversity do indeed exist in corporate environments. Inclusive recruitment policies, diversity committees, and diversity campaigns are particularly common practices adopted by the companies analyzed. However, on other points, this is not intended to promote factors such as innovation, talent retention, or a harmonious organizational climate. Among the responses, there is a predominance of cases in which these companies end up implementing inclusion and diverse initiatives to enhance their market image, or simply to comply with labor laws, such as the law on quotas for people with disabilities, demonstrating a lack of genuine concern for the issue and its employees.

Furthermore, it is significant to highlight, above all, the interviewees' predominant view of leadership performance as a fundamental factor for the process of working and generate benefits for both employees and employers. As previously mentioned in research, this function must be performed with a view to effective implementation and the enrichment of the organizational environment, as well as its potential for innovation and adaptability.

Regarding how these companies face discrimination and prejudice in the job market, only two interviewees stated the existence of a reporting or *compliance program*. In contrast, the others reported the absence or trivialization of the issue in everyday life. In addition, when we analyze the responses regarding the attractiveness of an environment with a well-structured inclusive culture, there is unanimous agreement that it is justified by a welcoming environment, which demonstrates a willingness to embrace differences and promote the integration of talents with employee well-being in mind.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Based on the analysis of collected data and studies conducted on the topic, an

inclusive organizational culture is a key factor for people management when implemented in a structured and efficient manner, aiming not only to promote diversity but also to create a more harmonious and innovative organizational environment. Therefore, by valuing different perspectives and experiences, organizations meet a growing social demand and impact the well-being of their employees.

Despite this, the scenario presented in the data analysis demonstrates that, although the topic is relevant to organizations, implementing an inclusive culture in their daily work requires adjustments focused on their beliefs, values, and norms, as well as alignment between theory and practice, management, leadership, and employees. Furthermore, it is essential that this improvement process be continuous and that all parties involved are engaged in building an environment that enhances its sustainability, social awareness, and good long-term management.

This research provides a basis for future studies in strategic planning for managing diversity and inclusion within organizations. It can be expanded in the future by utilizing other methods and technologies to analyze new scenarios, aiming to enhance the safety, satisfaction, and development of the participating population.

REFERENCES

ANTUNES, Jociane Vieira dos Santos; TOLDO, Mariesa. Racial diversity management: a competitive advantage for Brazilian companies. 2014.

BARDIN, Laurence. Content Analysis. New York: Routledge, 2011, 229 p.

CALEFFE, LG; MOREIRA, H. Research methodology for the research teacher. Rio de Janeiro: DP&A, 2006.

CÁRCERES DA COSTA, G.; GONÇALVES ARAÚJO, LM; ARAÚJO FERREIRA, M.A. ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE: CONCEPTS AND TYPOLOGIES. Economic Bulletin (BOCA), Boa Vista, v. 6, n. 16, p. 20–27, 2021. Available at: <https://revista.ioles.com.br/boca/index.php/revista/article/view/299>. Accessed on: August 18, 2024.

CHIAVENATO, Idalberto. Organizational Behavior: The Dynamics of Organizational Success. 4th ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 2021.

DA FONSECA, SDSA Organizational culture: a brief survey of the concept. PROCESSUS JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT, LEGAL AND FINANCIAL STUDIES, DF, year 12, v. 12, n. 42, p. 84-97, Jan./Jul. 2021. Available at: <https://periodicos.processus.com.br/index.php/egjf/article/view/642/690>. Accessed on: August 18, 2024.

DELVAS, Rodrigo Leandro. THE IMPORTANCE OF WELCOME AND INTEGRATION IN ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE: The Welcome Manual as an instrument for the socialization of new employees of the Federal Institute of Triângulo Mineiro – A proposal. 2017. Dissertation (Master's in Administrative Consulting) - Polytechnic Institute of Porto, Higher Institute of Accounting and Administration of Porto, Porto, 2017.

DIAS, Reinaldo. *Sociology of Organizations*. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 2012.
DIAS, SR *Organizational climate and culture*. Christmas: Edunp, 2011.

FERREIRA, LL et al. Department of Diversity, Equity and Inclusion: a new business trend. *E-Acadêmica*, v. 3, n. 3, p. 9, 2022. Available at: <https://eacademica.org/eacademica/article/view/374>. Accessed on August 18, 2024.

FLEURY, MTL *MANAGING CULTURAL DIVERSITY: experiences of Brazilian companies*. ERA - *Journal of Business Administration*, São Paulo, v. 40, n. 3, p. 18-25, 2000.

FLORES, JG *Qualitative data analysis: applications for educational research*. Barcelona: PPU, 1994.

FRASER, MTD; GONDIM, SMG *From the other's speech to the negotiated text: discussions on the interview in qualitative research*. *Paidéia*, 14 (28), 139-152, 2004. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/paideia/a/MmkPXF5fCnqVP9MX75q6Rrd/?lang=pt>. Access on: October 19, 2024.

GLASER, BG; STRAUSS, AL *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. New York: Aldine Publishing Company, 1967.

JUDGE, Timothy A.; ROBBINS, Stephen P. *Fundamentals of Behavior Organization*. 12th ed. São Paulo: Pearson, 2014.

NKOMO, SM; COX Jr., T. *Diversity and identity in organizations*. In: CLEGG, SR et al., *Handbook of organizational studies*, São Paulo: Atlas, 1998.

RENNER, JS; GOMES, G. *Diversity in organizations: from affirmative action to the management process*. *Knowledge & Diversity*, v. 12, n. 27, p. 27, 2020. Available at: https://revistas.unilasalle.edu.br/index.php/conhecimento_diversidade/article/view/6705. Accessed on: August 18, 2024.

TATAGIBA, ANK. *How can organizational culture impact your project's day-to-day activities? Project Management "E-book without Borders": PMI Distrito Federal and PMI Paraíba, 2022*. Available at: https://pmidf.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/E-BOOK-1-_22-Portugues-Cultura-Organizacional-1.pdf. Accessed on: August 18, 2024.

VIANA, Camilla Cristine. *ALIGNING ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND STRATEGY: AN ANALYSIS USING THE COMPETING VALUES FRAMEWORK*. 2024. Specialization (MBA in Strategic Management) - Applied Social Sciences, Federal University of Paraná, Curitiba, 2024.

VINUTO, J. *Snowball sampling qualitative research: an open debate*. *Thematics*, Campinas, SP, 10.20396/thematics.v22i44.10977. v. 22, n. 44, p. 203–220, 2014. Available at: <https://econtents.bc.unicamp.br/inpec/index.php/tematicas/article/view/10977>. Accessed: October 19, 2024.

ZANELLI, JC; BORGES-ANDRADE, JE; BASTOS, AVB *Psychology, organizations and work in Brazil*. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2004. p. 466 – 491.

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